

"Exploring *Candida albicans* and its related species: A comprehensive overview of its history, biology, taxonomy, life cycle, genetics, genomics, diseases, epidemiology and clinical Implications"

**Pankaj Mehrotra, PhD in Medical Sciences at Institute of Medical Sciences,
University of Aberdeen, Scotland, United Kingdom (2010-2014).**

Email : mehrotra85pankaj@gmail.com

A brief history of the genetics of *C. albicans*

A brief history of the genetics of *C. albicans* Oral Candida infections caused by the human fungal pathogen *Candida albicans* was described as early in the 2nd century AD by Galen as "ad aphthas albus" (McCullough et al., 1996). However it was not until in 1846, the first clinical diagnosis of a patient with "thrush" was formally reported by Berg. In 1847, Charles Philippe Robin characterized this type of oral infection as being caused by "*Oidium albicans*" thereby miss-classifying the organism as a fungus which grew on plants. In 1923, Christine Berkhout and others reclassified this fungus into genus *Candida* (Knoke and Bernhardt, 2006). The name *C. albicans* was officially endorsed by the 8th Botanical Congress committee in 1954 within the phylum Ascomycota, subphylum Saccharomycotina, which is the currently used classification (Odds, 1987; Calderone, 2002).

C. albicans is one of the many known yeasts with no known sexual cycle and the genus *Candida* contains many species that share this phenotype but are only distantly related to each other. In recent years research has led to the identification of a mating locus (Hull and Johnson, 1999; Hull et al., 2000; Magee and Magee, 2000) and subsequently conditions whereby mating of competent diploid strains in the so-called opaque phase cell type could fuse resulting in formation of tetraploid

progeny (Bennett et al., 2005). In 1985, David Soll's group discovered the phenomenon of phenotypic switching in 3153A strain of *C. albicans* and subsequently in the WO-I (white to opaque) strain of *C. albicans* (Slutsky et al., 1985; Slutsky et al., 1987). Mating was further linked to phenotypic switching in 2002 by Miller and Johnson, who showed that the mating competent opaque form could generate tetraploids at frequencies that were comparable with mating haploids of *S. cerevisiae*. The wild type laboratory strain of *C. albicans*, SC3514 genome was sequenced at Stanford Genome Technology centre (Jones et al., 2004) and the most recent annotation of this genome has been revised extensively (Butler et al., 2009). The genome of the WO-I strain of *Candida albicans* was subsequently sequenced by the Broad Institute of MIT and Harvard. The sequenced genomes of *C. albicans* contain many of the genes required for meiosis, but population structure analyses suggest that meiosis is rare or absent from extant clinical isolates. Recently, quasi-stable haploid strains were identified in *C. albicans* (Hickman et al., 2013) that could mate to regenerate diploids. However, despite these advances, no formal demonstration of meiosis has yet been observed in *C. albicans*. Should this occur the genus name of this important medical name would have to be reconsidered to reflect its new phylogeny!

Genome organisation

Considerable changes in genome size and the composition were found among different *Candida* species. *C. albicans* has a genome size of 14.3 Mb, 33.5 % GC content, with 6107 genes with an average gene size of 1468 base pairs (Butler et al., 2009) but with protein coding genes in the range of 5733 to 6318 bp. Interestingly with the exception of *C. glabrata* and *C. krusei* all the *Candida* species in the *C. albicans* clade translate the CUG codon as serine instead of leucine (Santos and

Tuite, 1995; Massey et al., 2003). This feature has made expression of heterologous proteins difficult in most *Candida* species, although codon-corrected reagents for genetic analyses have circumvented the problems associated with this non canonical codon reassignment. Phylogenetic analysis of *Candida* genomes has identified 9,209 gene families associated with pathogenicity and virulence. For example, *Candida* species have more or less expanded gene families encoding cell wall proteins such as Hyr1, Als and Pga30-, genes encoding extracellular enzymes such as lipases, phospholipases and proteases as well as stress response genes and genes associated with morphogenetic changes (Jones et al., 2004). Comparison of the genomes of *C. albicans* and *C. dubliniensis* revealed that these two species are highly syntenic, but 168 species-specific genes exist that include some encoding known hypha-specific virulence factors, including the Sap4 and Sap5 secreted aspartyl proteases and the adhesin and invasin Als3 which are absent from the *C. dubliniensis* genome (Jackson et al., 2009). The expansion of certain virulence-associated gene families often occurs in the sub-telomeric regions – such as with the EPA family of adhesins of *C. glabrata* (Kaur et al., 2007). The genetic diversity of such cell wall proteins within a species is often further increased by expansion of repeat regions within the gene. Genetic diversity within and between species is further increased by recombination events that have taken place between Major Repeat Sequences (MRS) found in *C. albicans* and *C. dubliniensis*, and sequences related to vestigial retro-transposons. Furthermore, genome sequencing has revealed the presence of most of the genes required for a sexual cycle in *C. albicans* including the mating type genes at two loci MLT α and MLT β , which are present on chromosome 5 (Jones et al., 2004). To study patho-genomics a database has been established Candida Genome

database (d'Enfert et al., 2005). Recently a bioinformatics tool “The Candida Gene Order Browser (CJOB)” has also been used to study the evolutionary relationship between multiple *Candida* species (Maguire et al., 2013).

Taxonomy of non-*albicans* *Candida* species

There are around 150 species of *Candida*, of which only a few are of medical importance (Odds, 1987). Most healthy individuals carry single strains and single species of *Candida* but some immune-compromised individuals may carry more than one species and multiple strains (Hunter et al., 1990). *C. albicans* mainly resides in the gastrointestinal tract (GI) and vaginal mucosa, however if present in high numbers and if normal protective immunity is impaired, candidemia (presence of *Candida* in blood) can occur, resulting in dissemination to the major internal organs. The medically important *Candida* species belong to the so-called CTG clade in which the canonical CTG codon encodes serine rather than leucine (Santos and Tuite, 1995). Within this group, the medically important species are *C. albicans*, *C. dubliniensis*, *C. tropicalis*, *C. lusitanae*, and *C. guilliermondii* (Fitzpatrick et al., 2006). *Candida* species are the most common cause of fungal infection in Europe but second most common in USA after dermatophytes (Marchetti et al., 2004; Wisplinghoff et al., 2004). More than 80% of *Candida* infections contributed in the world by species of *Candida* are due to *C. albicans*, *C. glabrata*, *C. parapsilosis*, *C. tropicalis* and *C. krusei* (Pfaller and Diekema, 2007; Pfaller et al., 2009). Although, *C. albicans* is the most prevalent species causing human infections in some countries a change in the prevalence and epidemiology of *Candida* infections has been reported. For example, in the Iberian peninsula in South America and India a shift from *albicans* to non-*albicans* species including *C. glabrata*, *C. tropicalis*, and *C. parapsilosis* has been observed (Krcmery and Barnes, 2002; Oberoi et al., 2012). In

India rare species of the *Candida haemulonii* complex have overtaken species such as *C. glabrata* in terms of prevalence (Oberoi et al., 2012).

Epidemiology

C. albicans lives as a commensal in the gastrointestinal tract, and on the oral and vaginal mucosa of all healthy individuals, however over-growth, trauma and immune suppression can lead to infections of mucosal membranes commonly known as thrush (Odds, 1987). These types of infections are common in gastrointestinal, vaginal, oral-pharyngeal mucosa and are also referred to as pseudomembranous candidiasis (Calderone, 2002). Oral pharyngeal candidiasis (OPC) is the most common form of infection in individual with immune-dysfunction e.g. Human immune-deficiency virus (HIV)-infected individuals (Coleman et al., 1993; Klein et al., 1984). OPC infections are mainly caused by *C. albicans* but other species of *Candida* such as *C. dubliniensis*, *C. glabrata* and *C. tropicalis* can also lead to OPC (Coleman et al., 1993; Sullivan et al., 2005). There has been a considerable decrease in the OPC infections in recent years due to the success of the use of potent antiviral therapy and prophylactic use of fluconazole in HIV-infected individuals. Most women (approximately 75%) are diagnosed with vulvo vaginal candidiasis (VVC) at least once in their life span, and more than 75 million women suffer from more than four episodes of VVC each year (Sobel, 1997; Brown et al., 2012). VVC is usually caused by *C. albicans* (90%) although some are due to *C. glabrata* (8%) (Sobel, 2006; Sobel, 2007). VVC infections are associated with the over use of reproductive hormones, antibiotic treatments etc. and these types of infections are usually treated by the use of fluconazole and caspofungin (Sobel, 2006; Sobel, 2007). There is also some evidence that women with recurrent VVC have alterations in the normal mucosal immune response (Sobel, 1997).

Candidemia, Candidiasis and Candidurea

Infections caused by *C. albicans* can become life-threatening, when *C. albicans* cells are able to penetrate through the epithelial cell barrier and enter the blood stream (candidemia or disseminated candidiasis) which can cause acute or chronic infection (Perlroth et al., 2007; Koh et al., 2008). In normal healthy individuals, innate immune cells (mainly neutrophils and macrophages) provide protection against *C. albicans*. Individuals who undergo chemotherapy tend to have low neutrophil counts (neutropenia), and gastrointestinal surgery often results in damage of epithelial wall leading to increased opportunity for entry of *C. albicans* into the blood. Candida is normally only able to enter the blood stream in severely immune compromised patients, but when it does, it can colonize the major organs, (disseminated candidiasis). Mortality rates for disseminated disease are between 30%-50% (Pfaller et al., 1998; Kibbler et al., 2003; Pfaller and Diekema, 2007), despite administration of antifungal drugs.

Candida species are also capable of forming biofilms on implanted devices such as catheters, prosthetic heart-valves and other implanted medical devices. This is an increasing and serious clinical problem, because fungal cells growing within a biofilm typically demonstrate increased resistance to a variety of antifungal drugs (reviewed by (Douglas, 2002; Ramage et al., 2013).

Other species of *Candida* associated with blood stream infections include *C. parapsilosis* infections of infants and neonates, *C. krusei* infections of patients' with haematological malignancies and bone marrow transplants, and *C. guilliermondii* infections of cardiovascular or gastrointestinal surgery patient's etc. (Levy et al., 1998; Fidel et al., 1999; Sullivan et al., 2005; Pfaller and Diekema, 2007; Giri and

Kindo, 2012). Intensive care unit patients can develop sepsis with *Candida* species leading to candidurea (Sobel et al., 2007). Recent studies have shown the occurrence of candidurea is around 10% in patients with prolonged candidemia. The risk factors such as CVCs, surgical procedures involving urinary tract infections and prolonged use of urinary catheters are often associated with development of this disease (Calderone, 2002).

Overview of biology of C. albicans

Life cycle and cell cycle of *C. albicans*

An important feature of biology of *C. albicans* is that it can grow in different morphological forms under different environmental niche conditions (Figure 1.1). The major important morphological forms of *C. albicans* are yeast cells, pseudo-hyphae, hyphae and chlamydo spores. In the normal yeast cell cycle, the yeast bud develops in the G1 phase of the cell cycle around the time of initiation of DNA replication. Nuclear division is followed by cytokinesis in the mother-bud neck, resulting in the formation of the daughter yeast and mother cells (Hazan et al., 2002). Pseudo-hyphae are formed, when the G2 phase of cell cycle is prolonged, and cell elongation results in formation of extended yeast cells that undergo synchronous rounds of division (Kron and Gow, 1995; Finley and Berman, 2005; Berman, 2006). True, non-constricted hyphae are formed first by elongation of evaginations from yeast cells to form germ tubes. Nuclear division and branching of the germ tube and branch formation is often delayed by one or more cell cycle generations (Sudbery et al., 2004). Chlamydo spores are asexual spores that are formed in media containing complex carbohydrates. They are formed by budding events from suspensor cells,

which are present on tip of hyphal or pseudohyphal cells (Jansons and Nickerson, 1970; Staib and Morschhauser, 2007). In recent years other cell types of *C. albicans* have been described (Gow, 2013). As mentioned above another important morphology in *C. albicans* is the White to Opaque cell transition (Slutsky et al., 1987). Opaque cells are competent for mating and are ellipsoidal and have pimples on their surface that differ from normal “white” phase yeast cells (Soll et al., 1993; Bailey et al., 1996). The transcription factor Wor1 plays an important role in controlling white-opaque switching (Miller and Johnson, 2002; Zordan et al., 2006). Other transcription factors which regulate this white-opaque switching are Czf1, Wor2, and Efg1 (Zordan et al., 2006). In *C. albicans* Mating Type Locus (MTLa or α) is located on chromosome (Hull and Johnson, 1999). The MTLa locus contains two mating types genes $a1$ and $a2$, and MTL α containing $\alpha1$ and/or $\alpha2$ (Hull and Johnson, 1999; Schaefer et al., 2007; Wu et al., 2007). Most strains are heterozygous ($a \alpha$), although a few clinical isolates are homozygous for the mating locus (Miller and Johnson, 2002). The MTLa1 and MTL α 2 forms a $a1$ - $\alpha2$ complex which inhibits mating by inhibiting a and α gene expression and loss of this ability to form $a1$ - $\alpha2$ complex in homozygous cells (MTLa a or MTL $\alpha\alpha$) promotes mating either by induction of a genes by MLTa2 locus in a MTL a cell and inducing of α genes MTL α 1 in a MTL α cell respectively (Magee and Magee, 2000; Lockhart et al., 2003). As shown in Figure 1.1., loss of diploidy through non-meiotic concerted chromosome loss results in formation of *C. albicans* haploid yeast cell which forms a diploid yeast either by self mating or cross mating to form a diploid yeast cells. As shown (Figure 1.1), that when *C. albicans* aa and $\alpha\alpha$ cells mate they form of elongated shmoo cells of aa and $\alpha\alpha$ cells and these shmoo cells (aa and $\alpha\alpha$) fuse to form a conjugation tube, which further fuses to form the zygote (Lockhart et al.,

2003). In this zygotic cell, the nucleus is tetraploid and divides by mitosis with one nucleus entering the subsequent daughter cells. (Bennett et al., 2005) .Tetraploid cells gradually revert to the diploid state cell by loss of chromosomes as shown (Figure1.1) (Bennett and Johnson, 2003; Hickman et al., 2013).

Figure 1. 1 Life cycle of *C. albicans*

This life cycle showing different morphological forms of *C. albicans* yeast cell, hyphae, pseudo-hyphae and chlamydospore, formation of white and opaque cells, development and fusion of shmoo leads to formation of tetraploid.

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